

EVIDENCE-BASED TOXICOLOGY
An open science journal for environmental health research

EBT Author Responses to Evaluation Comments for **TEBT- 2024-0010**

Summary of response to comments

We thank the peer reviewers for their time and comments on our protocol. We clarified our PECO criteria in accordance with the reviewer comments. Specifically, we revised our Population and Exposure criteria to better reflect our exclusion of occupational populations. We also updated the study designs eligible for inclusion in our study.

We explained how we plan to handle incident and prevalent outcomes and made corresponding revisions to the protocol. While we plan to include both types of health outcomes, we will keep incident and prevalent outcomes separate from one another during meta-analysis.

In our response, we also explained how our planned review is different from other similar reviews already in the literature. Namely, our scope differs from other existing reviews (O'Connor et al., 2017; Son et al., 2024), as does our choice of risk of bias tool, Navigation Guide. We provided an explanation of our choice of Navigation Guide as opposed to other, newer risk of bias tools.

Comment-by-comment responses

Ref.	Evaluation Comment	Response
1. Overall impressions of the planned research		
	<p><i>Reviewer comments</i></p> <p>1. In my opinion this review has strong potential for clarifying associations between exposure to animal feeding operations and health impacts.</p>	<p>We thank the reviewer for taking the time to review our protocol and for their comments.</p>
	<p>2. This protocol depicts an interesting topic and I enjoyed reading it. The protocol was well-developed in terms of the methods and reporting.</p>	<p>We thank the reviewer for taking the time to review our protocol and for their comments.</p>
2. Are the research questions important and sufficiently contextualised?		
	<p><i>Editor's summary of reviewer comments and suggestions for responding</i></p> <p>3. There were no reviewer comments directly relevant to this question, though the authors should be alert to implications of any comments in this report for how they contextualise their planned research - it seems quite a lot of reviewing has already been done (or is being planned) in a space with relatively few studies, so the contribution of the planned systematic review should be made very clear.</p>	<p>While there have been two recent systematic reviews on this topic (O'Connor et al., 2017; Son et al., 2024), we believe there are key differences between our planned systematic review and the existing systematic reviews. Many studies have been published since O'Connor et al. (2017), indicating the need for an updated review. While the Son et al. (2024) review was published recently, their research question and scope is different than ours. Specifically, Son et al. (2024) included studies that assessed exposures without health outcomes, whereas we are targeting studies that assess both an exposure and health outcome. Son et al. (2024)'s research question also explicitly involved environmental justice outcomes and for these reasons, we believe our scope is broader than that of Son et al. (2024).</p> <p>We also plan to evaluate Risk of Bias (RoB), whereas Son et al. (2024) did not perform a RoB assessment. O'Connor et al. (2017) used</p>

		<p>the ROBINS-E method to conduct their RoB assessment, and we plan to use the Navigation Guide. We believe that reviewing the body of literature using a different Risk of Bias tool is an important contribution to the literature. Another key way that our review differs from previous reviews is that we lack a financial conflict of interest, whereas O'Connor et al. (2017) had what we consider to be a significant financial conflict of interest.</p> <p>We plan to search the references of both O'Connor et al. (2017) and Son et al. (2024) for relevant studies.</p>
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3. Are the proposed research objectives logical, rational, and/or plausible?

	<p><i>Reviewer comments</i></p> <p>5. Could you clarify if you are evaluating association or causation?</p>	<p>The ultimate goal of our research is to evaluate whether there is evidence supporting a causal relationship between community exposure to animal operations and the hypothesized health outcomes. However, the studies in the literature may not lend themselves to causality as it difficult to conduct a randomized control trial addressing our research question. We recognize that the literature is predominantly observational studies that estimate associations between our exposure and outcomes of interest, but these associations can inform an assessment of causation. To address the potential for causality, we will incorporate robust methods for evaluating the quality of evidence and strength of association observed in these studies. This includes applying established criteria, such as temporality, strength, consistency, biological plausibility, and dose-response relationships, to critically assess the causal framework. While observational studies alone cannot definitively establish causality, the associations they reveal can significantly inform an evidence-based assessment through a critical assessment of causal elements informing understanding of the potential health impacts of community exposure to animal operations.</p>
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6a. **Population:** I know the authors have attempted to make this clear, but it isn't clear to me that, if the primary studies have participants who have occupational exposure to animal feeding operations then they are excluded from the review. In reality, at the primary level these studies usually make it really clear if people who live for work on farms, so they can readily be excluded. This matters for many of the outcomes – in particular the GIT infectious ones are often evaluated using ecological metrics at the county or region level and they can clearly include farm-based populations which have a different risk profile and therefore association with these outcomes than community populations. There might be several ways to make this clearer how you will deal with this. One option might be to say change the hypothesis.

i. For example, I am assuming that the clarification about “solely” excluded occupations was included to enable the inclusion of ecological studies predominately and also hospital based case-case or case-control studies for Staph aureus. If that is the case, then perhaps the best option is to be explicit and separate the hypothesis by individual level studies from those hypotheses that can include both community and occupational populations. This could give you something like the following, to enable recognition that both populations are included:

ii. For individual level research the question could be: People with community-based exposures to animal feeding operations are more likely to experience adverse respiratory health outcomes compared to people living further from animal feeding operations. This would

We thank the reviewer for this comment. We respectfully disagree with the statement that studies usually make it clear if participants work and/or live on farms. Often studies do not provide data on participant occupation, if exposures are evaluated using participant home address. For example, (Poulsen et al., 2018) highlights the lack of occupational data on their participants as a limitation of their paper, because they cannot determine the exact cause of environmental transmission (i.e., residential proximity or occupational exposure). We anticipate similar limitations in other studies, but ultimately, this will be assessed during our RoB assessment. We agree with the reviewer about the potential for bias in the exposure measurements for ecological studies. The uncertainty associated with exposure in ecological studies will be addressed in our Risk of Bias assessment. We also do not plan to separate our hypotheses into individual level and ecological level because the biases associated with ecological studies will be accounted for in our Risk of Bias assessment. We have clarified our Population and Exposure criteria in our PECOS table as follows:

enable removing studies that included farmers and occupation exposures like vets from MRSA studies.

iii. For ecological studies which can include off-farm (community) and on-farm populations (occupational) the hypothesis could be: Communities with animal feeding operations are experiencing higher adverse respiratory health rates compared to communities without animal animal feeding operations.

	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Population	Human populations, including those in utero	Any populations that are explicitly identified by their occupation or participation in activities involving direct exposure to livestock (e.g., occupational exposures, pastoralism, living on a farm, having animals in the home or backyard)
Exposure	Community/indirect exposure (e.g., residential, school) to an animal feeding operation estimated/assessed using any relevant metric, including distance to the nearest operation, farm and/or animal density, perceived odor, or levels of an indicator contaminant (e.g., endotoxins)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Studies without an exposure to an animal feeding operation • Direct exposure to livestock animals (see Population exclusion criteria). • Indirect exposure via a relative who works on a farm

6b. **Health outcomes.** Can you clarify if you will restrict to incident health outcomes and how you will handle prevalent outcomes area. This is important from a causal inference perspective as the population assumptions required for prevalent outcomes to be relevant. For pneumonia – I am assuming that also includes Q-fever based pneumonia and the other non-specific category reported in the Netherlands studies.

We thank the reviewer for bringing this to our attention. We plan to include both prevalent and incident outcomes, as both provide valuable information for understanding potential health impacts of community exposure to animal operations. However, we will keep these outcomes separate during meta-analysis. We have clarified our Outcome Inclusion Criteria in our PECOS table to reflect this:

	Inclusion Criteria
Outcome	Any clinical, surrogate, or patient-centered health outcome; either incident or prevalent outcomes

We have also updated our main body of text to reflect this:

“We will include all eligible in our meta-analysis and will not exclude studies based on their compatibility with others. Instead, we will stratify analyses where necessary to ensure meaningful comparisons and robust synthesis of evidence, including separating incident and prevalent outcomes. This approach enables us to leverage the diversity in study designs and populations while maintaining the integrity and inclusivity of the evidence base.” (Lines 272-276)

		<p>Regarding pneumonia: we will consider non-specific pneumonia to inform our hypothesis on respiratory health outcomes. We will consider Q-fever based pneumonia as informing both our infectious disease and respiratory health outcome hypotheses.</p>
	<p>6c. Exposures. To me the term “community-based exposure” is confusing as it is using the same terms to refer to the population – community-based population. I’m wondering if a better way to say the exposure was “off farm: exposure” or “no direct animal contact exposure”. Those terms could then be incorporated into the hypotheses related to individual animals and then it would be clear when studies don’t meet that definition. I know these terms haven’t been used before, but I wonder if it would be clearer. For example, “off -farm/off site exposure to an animal feeding operation(s) assessed using any relevant metric, including distance to the nearest operation, farm and/or animal density, perceived odor, or levels of an indicator contaminant (e.g., endotoxins). Just an idea to consider.</p>	<p>We chose the term “community exposure” to reflect our inclusion of populations with exposures resulting from the location of their home or school (or other relevant community location that is not an animal feeding operation or place of work). However, we acknowledge the nuance associated with assessing these types of exposures.</p> <p>We have reservations about excluding any “direct contact with animals”, as there may be studies focused on community exposures that do not provide information on participants’ occupations or their personal owning of food animals, for example. Poulsen et al. (2018) highlights a lack of participant occupation data as a limitation of their study on residential exposure to animal feeding operations. We plan to exclude studies that are occupational in nature, are of pastoralist populations, or of participants who live on a farm. We also plan to exclude studies that are interested in exposure to animals in the backyard or home and do not assess exposures resulting from living near animal feeding operations.</p> <p>We plan to account for an uncertainty in exposure assessment during our RoB process. Studies within our inclusion criteria that do not have data on occupation or household animals, for example, may receive a higher risk of bias rating as a result of the uncertainty in exposure source.</p>

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	<p>7. Comments relating to eligibility criteria.</p> <p>a. I think it would be helpful to say the study designs that are eligible. The eligible studies types are not reported here so you could use PECOS instead of PECO. I recognize they are included in the search so including them in the PECOS would be clearer.</p>	<p>In our original submission, we included our study designs of interest in our PECO table. We have changed our table to be a PECOS table (Table 4.6.1).</p>									
	<p>b. The authors may want to add the type of study they aimed at. For example, do the authors include case reports or case series study?</p>	<p>We thank the reviewers for bringing this to our attention. We have clarified the type of studies we are aiming for in Lines 179-181:</p> <p>“Articles will be eligible for this review when they describe peer-reviewed primary research in which populations with exposures to animal feeding operations are compared on an individual- or population-level basis to less- or not-exposed populations for any health outcome.”</p> <p>We plan to include case reports/studies and case series in our synthesis of evidence, but not in our meta-analysis, because they lack a comparator group. We have updated our PECOS table (Table 4.6.1) to reflect our inclusion of case reports/studies and case series:</p>									

		<table border="1" data-bbox="857 222 1484 438"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="857 222 971 243"></th> <th data-bbox="971 222 1198 243">Inclusion Criteria</th> <th data-bbox="1198 222 1484 243">Exclusion Criteria</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="857 243 971 438">Study Design</td> <td data-bbox="971 243 1198 438"> Epidemiologic studies including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Case-control • Case-cohort • Case-case • Cohort • Cross-sectional • Longitudinal • Ecological Case reports and case series^a </td> <td data-bbox="1198 243 1484 438"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reviews (e.g., systematic, scoping, narrative) • Meta analyses • Predictive modeling studies </td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p data-bbox="857 453 1484 516">The PECOS table will be accompanied by the following footnote:</p> <p data-bbox="857 541 1484 772">“a. For inclusion in meta-analysis, studies must have at least one comparator group. We will include case reports/studies and case series without comparator groups for additional evidence as part of our synthesis but will not include them in meta-analysis.” (Lines 589-591)</p>		Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria	Study Design	Epidemiologic studies including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Case-control • Case-cohort • Case-case • Cohort • Cross-sectional • Longitudinal • Ecological Case reports and case series ^a	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reviews (e.g., systematic, scoping, narrative) • Meta analyses • Predictive modeling studies
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	<p data-bbox="224 831 829 1150">c. "Articles will be eligible for this review when they describe peer-reviewed primary research in which people living in communities with exposures to animal feeding operations are compared to less- or not-exposed populations for any health outcome." How does this statement relate to ecological studies?</p>	<p data-bbox="857 831 1484 957">We thank the reviewer for bringing this to our attention. We have revised this statement to better reflect our inclusion of ecological studies:</p> <p data-bbox="857 982 1484 1213">“Articles will be eligible for this review when they describe peer-reviewed primary research in which populations with exposures to animal feeding operations are compared on an individual- or population-level basis to less- or not-exposed populations for any health outcome.” (Lines 179-181)</p>						
	<p data-bbox="224 1272 829 1839">d. Table 1 excludes occupational exposure studies, but the rationale for this is unclear. Many people may live near animal feeding operations and might also work on them, introducing potential bias. Even though the authors are using the PECO framework to articulate their objectives, the authors should consider this bias. [Editor’s note: It is not completely clear to me what the reviewer intends by this comment. If the issue is one of scope of the review, the authors may wish to explain why occupational exposure studies</p>	<p data-bbox="857 1272 1484 1692">Occupational exposure studies are outside the scope of our research question and would require different search strategy, as we are interested in indirect exposures to animal feeding operations. We acknowledge that study participants that live near animal feeding operations <i>may also work</i> at these operations and the inherent bias that this can introduce into our review. We exclude occupational populations and other populations that are chosen specifically because of their direct contact with animals. We have clarified this in our submission:</p> <p data-bbox="857 1717 1484 1864">“Additionally, while our focus is on community exposures (i.e., indirect exposures, excluding occupational studies), rural communities may include some people</p>						

	<p>are excluded from a “community exposure” systematic review. If this is a confounding or other bias issue, the authors may wish to clarify how their decision addresses this issue.]</p>	<p>who also work in animal feeding operations, raise backyard chickens, or otherwise experience direct exposures to animals. Community-based studies that do not explicitly exclude populations with direct exposure, or control for direct exposures in their analyses, introduce an important source of potential bias. Our risk of bias assessment will be critical in evaluating studies subject to these and other potential sources of bias.” (Lines 415-420)</p>
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4. Is the study set-up and data collection method feasible and appropriate for the research goals?

	<p><i>Reviewer comments</i></p> <p>8. This topic has approximately 10 populations (with multiple studies per population) and some publications with over 100 outcome-exposure measures. Some papers report 6 measures of exposure and 20 different outcomes. Will all outcome-exposure pairs be extracted and reported?</p>	<p>We are unsure of the 10 populations the reviewer is referring to in this question. We plan to document all exposure measurements and outcomes used in each study and provide a descriptive synthesis or table of these combinations. Then, during our synthesis and meta-analysis, we will extract the values of the measurements of associations that can will be pooled with one another. We acknowledge that this may be a significant amount of work, but this is a standard approach in systematic review and meta-analysis when exploring different exposures and health outcomes.</p>
	<p>9. Comments related to risk of bias</p> <p>a. Can you clarify how the chosen risk of bias tools apply to the different study designs? The Navigation guide doesn’t seem to differentiate between the study designs (case control, cohort, cross section etc) and seems very light on details. ROBINS-E does focus only on cohort studies. Nonetheless, it is the most explicit tool for risk of bias in observational studies, so why not use it at least for cohort studies? Please indicate how you will assess risk of bias for case-case, case-control, cross-</p>	<p>The Navigation Guide risk of bias tool was specifically developed to synthesize evidence from diverse study designs in a manner that ensures consistency and comparability across the entire body of evidence. Using a single, unified framework allows us to integrate fundings from case-control, cohort, and other observational study designs into an overall assessment of risk of bias and strength of evidence. This uniform approach ensures consistency in evaluating the strengths and weaknesses of individual studies while enabling integration into a comprehensive body of evidence. Applying different tools based on study design would introduce inconsistencies and make it impossible to compare studies or synthesize</p>

	<p>sectional (relevant outcomes) studies or ecological studies.</p>	<p>results into a cohesive evaluation of the evidence across all study types.</p> <p>While the Navigation Guide does not explicitly differentiate between study designs, it offers sufficient flexibility to evaluate key domains of bias across various methodologies, including selection bias, exposure and outcome assessment, and confounding. The evaluation criteria can be tailored to the nuances of different study designs. For example, it accounts for potential biases inherent to case-control studies (e.g., recall bias) and cohort studies (e.g., loss to follow-up), providing clear, structure guidance for reviewers. By using a consistent tool, researchers can integrate findings from diverse study designs to arrive at evidence-based conclusions without introducing additional variability from design-specific risk of bias tools.</p> <p>We recognize the strengths of tools such as ROBINS-E for evaluating cohort studies and other specific study designs, However, this tool has faced several criticism and challenges in its application, including issues with subjectivity, limited applicability (designed specifically for cohort studies), overly stringent criteria, and challenges in synthesizing results. It is because of these limitations that we concluded this would not be the most appropriate choice for this research study, particularly since we are anticipating a mix of study designs and would prefer a more streamlined, consistent methodology that has been validated in numerous case studies to date, leading to our ultimate decision to apply the Navigation Guide Risk of Bias tool.</p>
	<p>b. With respect to bias, it seems that collider stratification bias is being more commonly recognized in epidemiology. How will you assess this if not covered by the sources you are using?</p>	<p>Collider stratification bias is a form of selection bias wherein the exposure of interest and the outcome of interest are ancestors of participation in a study. Conditioning on, stratifying on, or restricting on the collider can induce bias. We should be able to assess this as a form of selection bias, but we also have the opportunity to capture this in the “other</p>

		<p>risk of bias” category if it comes up repeatedly in our review of the literature.</p>
	<p>c. With respect to studies that use prevalent health outcomes. One option is to consider them measures of burden of disease, separate from associations. Can you discuss your approach to this? If the goal is association, and adjustment for confounding, this implies a causal hypothesis but that requires some very strong population based assumptions. How will you assess if they meet the population? assumptions for use for causal inference measures? See e.g. (Alho 1992) and (Pearce 2004).</p>	<p>We thank the reviewer for bringing this to our attention. We plan to consider measures of association for prevalent health outcomes separate from those of incident health outcomes. We have revised our section on meta-analysis to reflect this:</p> <p>“We will include all eligible studies in our meta-analysis and will not exclude studies based on their compatibility with others. Instead, we will stratify analyses where necessary to ensure meaningful comparisons and robust synthesis of evidence, including separating incident and prevalent outcomes.” (Lines 272-275)</p>
	<p>10. [Editor’s comment from triage.] I am not entirely convinced about the authors’ arguments that they can only present a draft code book. An inductive coding strategy would be more typical for qualitative research, where the structure of the data cannot be known before analysis commences. For a systematic review that assesses the evidence for three quite precisely-articulated hypotheses, it is not so clear to me why at least the part of the coding that relates to abstracting the data that would support answering the research questions of the review cannot already be articulated. (While this is considerable work, there is benefit to including this in the protocol for the authors, as it allows us to comment on this before rather than after data is collected and coded.)</p>	<p>We thank the editor for their comment. We have provided a more extensive codebook in our supplemental materials, available at https://osf.io/4v52e/.</p> <p>We added codes to our codebook that cover the following variables: funding, conflict of interest statements, inclusion criteria, exclusion criteria, comorbidities, country, description of animal operation, unit of exposure metric, and effect modification.</p>

5. Is the planned method for data analysis and interpretation feasible and sound?

	<p><i>Reviewer comments</i></p> <p>10. The authors state they cannot provide meta-analysis due to the possibility of heterogenous data. However, they have also stated they will conduct subgroup analysis according to heterogeneity they are anticipating. It seems that the authors can anticipate meta-analysis among data which are similar for population characteristics, exposure characteristics, or outcome characteristics. If heterogeneity is such a major issue, the authors could narrow the purpose of their article.</p>	<p>We expect to conduct a meta-analysis and have updated our protocol to better reflect this. We do anticipate heterogeneity and thus have chosen to use a random-effects model to conduct the meta-analysis:</p> <p>“We plan to conduct a traditional meta-analysis to generate summary estimates that could provide insight into quantitative relationships between community exposure to animal operations and adverse human health outcomes.</p> <p>We will use a random-effects model to conduct our meta-analysis, as it allows for the inclusion of studies that may differ in populations, exposure measurements, outcomes, and study designs. Given the anticipated heterogeneity across these factors, a random-effects model is more appropriate than a fixed-effects model, as it accounts for variability both within and between studies.” (Lines 260-264)</p>
	<p>11. There may be a potential dose-response relationship between the exposures and health outcomes, why not try to establish such a relationship when data is available?</p>	<p>Our ultimate goal is to determine causality between our exposure and outcomes of interest, but the literature is predominantly observational studies that estimate associations between our exposure and outcomes of interest, which makes a dose-response meta-analysis challenging. If we</p>

		<p>have data that is sufficiently similar, we will conduct a dose-response meta-analysis.</p>
	<p>12. As there are currently almost (?) more reviews on this topic than studies, knowledge about this body of work is not absent – can you provide greater detail of the planned synthesis.</p>	<p>We have spent time with the literature and disagree with this assertion. As mentioned in our protocol, we estimate that approximately 375 papers will undergo full text screening for review, based on estimates from our screening pilot. Given the large number of anticipated studies, our broad range of health outcomes, and our current knowledge of the literature, we firmly believe that there are more studies on this topic than reviews.</p> <p>We have revised our section 2.8 Data Synthesis to better reflect our planned meta-analysis methods. Specifically, we have added our planned use of a random effects model for meta-analysis:</p> <p>“We plan to conduct a traditional meta-analysis to generate summary estimates that could provide insight into quantitative relationships between community exposure to animal operations and adverse human health outcomes.</p> <p>We will use a random-effects model to conduct our meta-analysis, as it allows for the inclusion of studies that may differ in populations, exposure measurements, outcomes, and study designs. Given the anticipated heterogeneity across these factors, a random-effects model is more appropriate than a fixed-effects model, as it</p>

		accounts for variability both within and between studies.” (Lines 256-264)
	13. Do you intend to combine estimates from studies that use prevalent outcomes and studies that use incident outcomes? If so, how?	We do not plan to combine incident and prevalent outcomes. Studies with incident outcomes will be considered for meta-analysis separate from prevalent outcomes: “Instead, we will stratify analyses where necessary to ensure meaningful comparisons and robust synthesis of evidence, including separating incident and prevalent outcomes.” (Lines 273-275)
	14. Can you address how you intend to cope with the multiplicity in the analyses. Some papers have over 100 outcomes-exposures measures i.e. some papers reported 6 measures of exposure and 20 different outcomes. How will this multiplicity be handled?	We recognize that some studies report a large number of exposure-outcome measures. We will extract all relevant combinations of exposure-outcome associations, and then evaluate them across studies, identifying those which have sufficient reporting to synthesize across studies and also taking into consideration other aspects of our review such as risk of bias evaluations for each study. In our synthesis process, we plan to combine health outcomes into pre-defined categories. These categories can be found in Table 4.
	15. How will you group health outcomes, what will you do with health outcomes that are not replicated? As the body of work is well known the concerns/concepts can be anticipated and preplanned?	During our analysis, we plan to combine health outcomes into pre-defined categories, when deemed appropriate. Health outcomes that are not replicated (only reported in one or a small number of studies) will be included but will not be included in a quantitative synthesis. Instead, these outcomes will be included in our narrative review.
	16. Any thoughts on how you synthesize studies that “ adjust for different confounders?	Synthesizing studies that adjust for different confounders is a standard consideration of a systematic review. We have previously identified key confounders of interest for our review (age, sex, socioeconomic status, race/ethnicity, BMI, exposure to environmental tobacco smoke; participant smoking status). These confounders were selected based on their relevance to the exposure and outcomes of interest. For each

		<p>included study, we plan on recording all confounders that were controlled for and assess alignment with our predetermined list. This information will directly inform our risk of bias assessment, as we will evaluate whether studies have adequately adjusted for critical confounders. Studies that fail to adjust for these key factors may be rated as having a higher risk of bias in the confounding domain. By systematically documenting and assessing the confounders considered across studies, we aim to provide a transparent and robust synthesis of the evidence that account for these differences. We will then take this into consideration when evaluating synthesizing studies, identifying studies that adjust for similar confounders and those that deviate from our pre-determined list.</p>
	<p>17. Any thoughts on synthesis of ecological studies ?</p>	<p>Ecological studies will be synthesized the same as other observational studies. If an ecological study includes a quantitative measure of association, we will include it and conduct a Risk of Bias assessment. Since we are evaluating the collective body of evidence, ecological studies will not be treated differently.</p>
	<p>18. The more recently published ROBINS-E starts with observational evidence at “low” – can you elaborate on why you’ve chosen the older approach.</p>	<p>We recognize that ROBINS-E has established a starting point for observational evidence as a “low” risk of bias, reflecting an effort to align with frameworks like GRADE, which place greater emphasis on evidence provided by randomized controlled trials.</p> <p>However, we have chosen to use the Navigation Guide risk of bias approach, which has been specifically developed for and extensively validated over time in the environmental health field. The Navigation Guide approach assigns an initial “moderate” quality rating to the body of human observational evidence. This initial quality rating aligns with the recognition of human observational studies as a reliable source of evidence in both clinical and environmental-health decision-making.</p> <p>We do not believe that more recent publication of ROBINS-E and its decision to</p>

		<p>establish a starting point for observational evidence as “low” is a reflection of the current scientific consensus regarding the utility of observational data in environmental health decision-making. It is instead a reflection of a decision to align specifically with approaches in clinical decision-making. We also note that this difference in approach does not necessarily result in divergent final ratings of the evidence. Both frameworks are designed to systematically evaluate the quality of evidence and account for study characteristics. While ROBINS-E starts observational studies at “low” and upgrades evidence for strengths, the Navigation Guide starts at “moderate” and allows for ratings upward or downward based on the similar considerations. Ultimately, both frameworks aim to reach an evidence rating that reflects the balance of strengths and limitations across the entire body of evidence.</p>
	<p>20. Can you clarify what is a “guarantor” of a review. It seems like it might be “I’m responsible for the entire review” which implies the other authors are not – if that is the correct interpretation perhaps you should specify what everyone is “responsible for”. If that isn’t the correct interpretation – perhaps clarify what it does mean.</p>	<p>The term “guarantor” was taken directly from item 3b in the PRISMA-P checklist, and it refers to the author who takes primary responsibility for the overall integrity and accuracy of the review process. This does not imply that the other authors are not responsible for the review; rather all authors (including the guarantor) share collective responsibility for the work. The guarantor specifically oversees this process and ensures that all aspects of the review adhere to the highest standards of transparency, rigor, and ethical conduct.</p>

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